

Synthesis of 3-Heteroaryl-4-hydroxybenzocarbostyrils

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Several new 3-heteroaryl-4-hydroxybenzocarbostyrils (3-5, 7-9, 11) have been prepared by condensation of 3-acetoacetyl (1), 3-cinnamoyl (6) and 3-glyoxalyl (10) derivatives with amines, hydrazines and semicarbazide, and their structures have been established by elemental analysis, ir and ¹H nmr spectral data.

The synthesis of several 3-substituted-4-hydroxycarbostyrils have been reported in the literature, however the synthesis of 4-hydroxybenzocarbostyrils with heterocyclic substituents at the 3-position is not reported yet. We described earlier the synthesis of some 3-heteroaryl-4-hydroxybenzocarbostyrils¹.

Thus, 3-acetoacetylbenzo(*h*)-4-hydroxycarbostyril (2a), 3-acetoacetylbenzo(*f*)-4-hydroxycarbostyril (2b) and 3-acetoacetyl-4-hydroxy-6-methylcarbostyril (2c) have been obtained by Claisen condensation of the corresponding 3-acetyl derivatives (1a-c) with ethyl acetate in the presence of sodium metal (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

Based on the reaction of β -diketones with hydrazines² and hydroxylamine with the formation of pyrazole and isoxazole derivatives, the products obtained from the reaction of 2a-c with these reagents may have formula 3a-f and 4a-c or possibly their isomeric formula 3i and 4i. Similar cyclisation condensation took place upon reacting the acetoacetyl derivatives (2a-c) with ethanolamine affording the oxazipine derivatives (5a-c) or the isomeric one (5i).

In continuation of preparing of carbostyrils having heterocyclic substituents at position-3, we reacted the α,β -unsaturated ketones (6a-c) with

hydrazines, hydroxylamine and ethanolamine. It was found that compounds 6a-c reacted with one equivalent of these reagents in boiling ethanol to give condensation products, resulted by the elimination of one mole of water. These products were identified as the 3-(pyrazolinyl)-4-hydroxycarbostyrils (7a-f), 3-(isoxazolinyl)-4-hydroxycarbostyrils (8a-c) and 3-(1,4-oxazipinyl)-4-hydroxycarbostyrils (9a-c). The reaction of 6a-c with hydrazines is comparable with that of 3-cinnamoyl-4-hydroxycoumarins towards the same reagents. The formation of compounds 7a-f, 8a-c and 9a-c possibly takes place via the mechanism shown in Scheme 2.

Scheme 2

The 3-acetyl derivative (1a-c) are oxidised by selenium dioxide in dioxane to give benzo(*h*)-3-glyoxalyl-4-hydroxycarbostyril (10a), benzo(*f*)-3-glyoxalyl-4-hydroxycarbostyril (10b) and 3-glyoxalyl-4-hydroxy-6-methylcarbostyril (10c) (Scheme 3). Compound 10c on condensation with NH₂OH gave the monoxime (11) which on treatment with semicarbazide HCl, semicarbazone of the type 12 was isolated. Acidic cyclisation of compound 12 with HCl give 3-hydroxy-5*H*-6-substituted-1,2,4-triazine (13) (Scheme 3).

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on an Unicam SP-1200 spectrophotometer, and ¹H nmr spectra (DMSO-d₆) on Varian EM 390 spectrometer with (CH₃)₄Si as internal standard. Compounds 1 and 6 were prepared by reported method¹. All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

3-Acetoacetylbenzo(h or f)-4-hydroxycarbostyril and 3-acetoacetyl-4-hydroxy-6-methylcarbostyril (2a–c): A mixture of 1a–c (0.03 mol), finely divided sodium metal (0.15 mol) and dry ethyl acetate (0.68 mol) was refluxed for 4 h. The reaction mixture was kept at room temperature overnight, then poured into dilute acetic acid and the resulting solids were washed with water and crystallised from AcOH and EtOH. The products (75–89%) had m.ps. >300°; 2b ν_{\max} 1 670, 1 660, 1 620 (3 α -, 3 γ -, 2'-C=O) respectively), 2 580 cm⁻¹ (OH at position-4); δ 11.6 (1H, br, OH exchangeable with D₂O), 7.2–9.0 (6H, m, ArH), 5.9 (H, NH), 3.2–4.1 (5H, br, β -CH₂ and CH₃).

4-Hydroxy-3-[(5 or 3)-methyl-(1 or 2)phenyl(or H)pyrazol-3 or 5-yl]benzo(h or f)carbostyril and 4-hydroxy-3-[5(or 3)-methyl-1 or H]-pyrazol-3- or 5-yl]-6-methylcarbostyril (3a–f): A mixture of each of 2a–c (0.002 mol), hydrazine hydrate and/or phenylhydrazine (0.002 mol) in ethanol (5 ml) was refluxed for 4 h and the solids were crystallised from AcOH and EtOH respectively. The products (60–75%) had m.ps. >300° except 3f, 217–20°; 3d ν_{\max} 3 400 (NH carbostyril), 2 560 (OH at position-2)

and 1 580 cm⁻¹ (C=N); δ 11.2–12.4 (2H, br, OH at position-4 and NH of pyrazole ring, exchangeable with D₂O), 7.3–9 (7H, m, pyrazole ring and ArH), 5.8 (NH of carbostyril) and 3.2 (3H, s, CH₃).

4-Hydroxy-3-[5(or 3)-methylisoxazol-3-(or 5)-yl]benzo(h or f)carbostyril and 4-hydroxy-6-methyl-3-[5-(or 3)-methylisoxazol-3-(or 5)-yl]carbostyril (4a–c): To a suspension of each of 2a–c (0.002 mol) in ethanol (5 ml) was added hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.002 mol). The mixture was refluxed for 6 h, then cooled and the solids deposited were crystallised from EtOH and DMF. All compounds (69–75%) had m.ps. >300°.

4-Hydroxy-3-[5'(or 7')-methyl-2',3'-dihydro-1',4'-oxazipin-7 (or 5)-yl]benzo(h or f)carbostyril and 4-hydroxy-3-[5'(or 7')methyl-2',3'-dihydro-1',4'-oxazipin-7 (or 5)-yl]-6-methylcarbostyril (5a–c): A mixture of 2a–c (0.0025 mol), ethanolamine (0.0025 mol) and absolute ethanol (5 ml) was refluxed for 4 h then cooled and the resulting solids were crystallised from EtOH and DMF. All compounds (64–70%) had m.ps. >300°; 5a ν_{\max} 3 400 (NH carbostyril), 3 500 (OH at position-4), 1 625 (C=O carbostyril), 1 580 (C=N) and 1 090 cm⁻¹ (C–O–C of cyclic ether).

4-Hydroxy-3-[5-phenyl (or 1,5-diphenyl)-2-pyrazolin-3-yl]benzo(h or f)carbostyril and 4-hydroxy-6-methyl-3-[5-phenyl (or 1,5-diphenyl)-2-pyrazolin-3-yl]carbostyril (6a–f): A suspension of each of 6a–c (0.0025 mol) in ethanol (5 ml) was treated with hydrazine and/or phenylhydrazine (0.0025 mol), and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 3 h. The resulting solids were crystallised from AcOH and DMF. All compounds (64–73%) had m.ps. >300° except 7d, 194–96° and 7f, 218–20°; 7c ν_{\max} 3 330 (NH carbostyril), 3 120 (NH pyrazole), 2 600 (OH carbostyril), 1 630 (C=O at position-2) and 1 600 cm⁻¹ (C=N).

Action of hydroxylamine on 6a–c. Formation of 4-hydroxy-3-[5-phenylisoxazolin-3-yl]benzo(h or f)carbostyril and 4-hydroxy-6-methyl-3-[5-phenylisoxazolin-3-yl]carbostyril (8a–c): A mixture of each of 6a–c (0.0035 mol) and hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.0035 mol) in ethanol (5 ml) was refluxed for 5–6 h and the resulting solids after cooling were crystallised from AcOH and EtOH. All compounds (69–72%) had m.ps. >300° except 8c, 220–22°.

4-Hydroxy-3-[7-phenyl 2,3,6,7-tetrahydro-1,4-oxazipin-5-yl]benzo(h or f)carbostyril and 4-hydroxy-6-methyl-3-[7-phenyl-2,3,6,7-tetrahydro-1,4-oxazipin-5-yl]carbostyril (9a–c): A mixture of each of 6a–c (0.0025 mol), ethanolamine (0.0025 mol) and absolute EtOH (5 ml) was refluxed for 4 h and the resulting solids were crystallised from AcOH: 9a, m.p. 297–99°, 9b, >300°, 192–93°; 9b ν_{\max} 3 300 (NH carbostyril), 2 540 (OH at position-4), 1 625 (C=O at position-2) and 1 580 cm⁻¹ (C=N).

Benzo(h)-3-glyoxalyl-4-hydroxycarbostyril (10a), benzo(f)-3-glyoxalyl-4-hydroxycarbostyril (10b) and 3-glyoxalyl-4-hydroxy-6-methylcarbostyril (10c): To a solution of 1a–c (0.0025 mol) in dioxan (5 ml),

selenium dioxide (0.0025 mol) was added. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 4 h and cooled to yield the products which were crystallised from AcOH. The compounds (80–90%) had m.p.s. $>300^{\circ}$; **10c** ν_{\max} 1 720, 1 680 and 1 635 cm^{-1} (3β , 3α and position-2 C=O respectively).

Condensation of 10c with hydroxylamine HCl. Formation of the monoxime (11): A suspension of **10c** (0.002 mol) in ethanol (50 ml) was treated with $\text{NH}_2\text{OH}\cdot\text{HCl}$ (0.002 mol) and the resulting solid was crystallised from EtOH, (90%), m.p. $>300^{\circ}$.

Semicarbazone (12): A suspension of **11** (0.0025 mol) in ethanol (100 ml) was treated with semicarbazide HCl (0.0025 mol) for a period of 30 min. The resulting solid after dilution was crystallised from EtOH, (80%), m.p. $>300^{\circ}$.

Acidic cyclisation of 12. Formation of 13: A mixture of **12** (2 g) and HCl (20 ml; 20%) was refluxed for 4 h and then cooled. The solid obtained was crystallised from AcOH, (80%), m.p. $>300^{\circ}$.

References

1. E. A. MOHAMED, *J. Chem. Soc. Pak.*, 1990; A. A. SAYED, S. M. SAMI, A. EL-FAYOMI and E. A. MOHAMED, *Egypt J. Chem.*, 1976, **19**, 811; A. A. SAYED, S. M. SAMI, A. EL-FAYOMI and E. A. MOHAMED, *Acta Chim. Acad. Sci. Hung.*, 1977, **94**, 131.
2. H. A. ZAHER, R. M. ABDEL-RAHMAN and A. M. ABDEL-HALIM, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1987, **26**, 719; R. M. ABDEL-RAHMAN, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1988, **27**, 548; *Pak. J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1989, **32**, 240.